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EOSC AAI Architecture 2022

EOSC-A AAI TF - Report

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1 Introduction

The Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure Architecture (AAI) Task Force aims to provide a consistent architecture for Authentication, Authorization and Access Control for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This report captures the current status of the EOSC AAI architecture discussions and identifies the challenges and the areas that require further work. Target audiences include AAI experts, operators of organisations providing services to the EOSC, organisations operating proxies that aggregate other service providers or enrich identities, and providers of authentication identities whose identities are used by EOSC services or by EOSC proxies. This report provides valuable insights to help these target groups understand, implement, and interoperate within the defined AAI architecture.

The current EOSC AAI architecture (version 2022) is based on the AARC Blueprint Architecture 2019 [[AARC-G045](#)]. The goal of the AAI TF is not to define a new AAI architecture, but rather to define an AAI architecture that follows the AARC BPA and the AARC Interoperability Guidelines. Specifically, the EOSC-A AAI Task Force has worked in collaboration with AEGIS [[AEGIS](#)], the AARC Community and other stakeholders to evolve the AARC Blueprint Architecture & Guidelines and use them as the basis for delivering the EOSC AAI Architecture 2022. The AARC BPA deployment model provides a baseline for integrating multiple AARC BPA deployments in an interoperable manner. The EOSC AAI Architecture 2022 defined in the document expands the deployment model to a federated model in order to enable integration without the need for bilateral agreements.

In addition, the document describes how to adopt AARC "hinting" specifications to streamline the discovery process and improve the user experience. It also discusses both short-term and long-term solutions to support multi-infrastructure workflows and outlines strategies for expanding access beyond research and education. Lastly, the document defines the technical interoperability requirements for both SAML and OpenID Connect entities.

2 Definitions and Terminology

The key words "MUST", "MUST NOT", "REQUIRED", "SHALL", "SHALL NOT", "SHOULD", "SHOULD NOT", "RECOMMENDED", "MAY", and "OPTIONAL" in this document are to be interpreted as described in RFC 2119 [[RFC2119](#)].

Common terms and definitions used in the context of the EOSC AAI:

Community: A group of users, organised with a common purpose, and jointly granted access to resources. It may act as the interface between individual users and the resources. (see also [[WISE-SCI](#)])

Digital identity: Information that represents an entity (subject) within a domain. It contains information about the subject's attributes and relationships.

Federation: Identity Federation. An association of organisations that come together to securely exchange information as appropriate about their users and resources to enable collaborations and transactions.

Federation Member: An organisation that has joined the Federation by agreeing to be bound by the Federation Policy.

Federation Operator: An organisation that is authoritative for a Federation. A Federation Operator administers the Trust Anchor(s) for entities in its Federation (see [[OIDC-Fed](#)]).

Federation Policy: A document describing the obligations, rights and expectations of the Federation Members and the Federation Operator.

Federation Registry: A system used by the Federation Operator to manage entities and their metadata. This may be via a self-service tool or via other manual processes.

Community identity: A user's Digital identity that may be enriched by the Community with additional attributes such as a shared user identifier, profile information, and community

attributes such as group membership and role information (see [\[REFEDS-R&S\]](#) and [\[REFEDS-Sirtfi\]](#)).

AAI service: A service that enables authenticated and authorised access to resources.

Community AAI: An AAI service that also enables the use and management of Community identities for access to resources. It comprises three (3) AARC BPA component layers: the Access Protocol Translation, the Community Attributes Services, and the Authorisation.

Infrastructure Proxy: An AAI service of a research infrastructure or e-Infrastructure (hereafter termed infrastructure) that enables access to resources offered by Service Providers connected to that infrastructure. This AAI service does not provide community membership management¹. Specifically, the Infrastructure Proxy comprises two (2) AARC BPA component layers: the Access Protocol Translation and the Authorisation.

Generic service: A service provided to users, possibly as members of different communities.

Community service: A service provided to members of a specific community.

Infrastructure service: A service provided by a research infrastructure or e-Infrastructure to members of one or more Community AAI which receives the required attributes through an Infrastructure Proxy.

Trust Anchor: An entity that represents a trusted third party (see [\[OIDCFed\]](#)).

¹ The Infrastructure proxy, as any other end service, can apply its own authentication and authorisation process concerning its protected resources. As such it may add Infrastructure specific attributes to the incoming identities. In other words, the authentication and authorisation process for accessing services may be based on a combination of information coming from more than one source, including the Infrastructure proxy.

3 AARC Blueprint Architecture

The basis of the EOSC AAI Architecture is the AARC Blueprint Architecture (AARC BPA) [AARC-G045], which provides a set of building blocks for software architects and technical decision makers who are designing and implementing access management solutions for international research collaborations.

Figure 1: Component layers of the AARC Blueprint Architecture (AARC-BPA-2019)

The AARC BPA includes five (5) component layers: *User Identity*, *Community Attribute Services*, *Access Protocol Translation*, *Authorisation*, and *End Services*.

As illustrated in Figure 1, each of these layers includes one or more functional components,

grouped by their complementary functional roles:

- *User Identity* - Contains services for the identification and authentication of users. In existing implementations in the research and education space, these services typically include Security Assertion Markup Language (SAML) identity providers, certification authorities and, more recently, OpenID Connect (OIDC) or OAuth2 Providers (OPs). Although the focus of the services in this layer is to provide user authentication, often some end-user profile information is released as part of the authentication process.
- *Community Attribute Services* - Groups components related to managing and providing information (attributes) about users. Typically, this information includes community group memberships and roles, which is added on top of the information that might be provided directly by the identity providers from the User Identity Layer. In addition to managing and providing information about users, the Community Attribute Services layer also enables the management of Acceptable Use Policies (AUP) and terms and conditions, which are essential for binding users to the intended purpose for which services and resources are made available.
- *Access Protocol Translation*. It includes the following services:
 - a. SP-IdP-Proxy (proxy), which serves as a single integration point between the Identity Providers from the User Identity Layer and the Service Providers in the End Services Layer. Thus, the proxy acts as an SP towards the Identity Federations for which this proxy looks like any other SP, while towards the internal SPs it acts as an IdP.
 - b. Token Translation Services, which translate identity tokens between different technologies.
 - c. Discovery Service, which enables the selection of the user's authenticating IdP.
 - d. User notice, which allows users to be informed regarding the processing of their personal data

- *Authorisation* - Contains components for controlling access to the End Services Layer. The AARC BPA allows the implementers to delegate many of the complex authorisation decisions to central components, which can significantly reduce the complexity of managing authorisation policies, and their evaluation for each service individually. Different authorisation models can be supported depending on the authorisation requirements of each service:
 - a. Centralised Policy Information Point: the Proxy aggregates user attributes, such as group membership information and roles, and makes them available to the end-services which in turn can take the authorisation decision and enforce access control.
 - b. Centralised Policy Management and Decision Making: the Proxy conveys the authorisation decision to the end-services in the form of resource capabilities [[AARC-G027](#)]. End-services can enforce access control based on the received resource capabilities.
 - c. Centralised Policy Management and Decision Making and Enforcement: the Proxy enforces the decision directly at the proxy

These models streamline authorisation management by allowing to centralise complex decision-making processes, while providing flexibility for services that require full control over the authorisation.

- *End-services* - Contains the services users want to use. Access to these services is protected (using different technologies). These services can range from simple web-browser-based services, such as wikis or portals for accessing computing and storage resources, to non-web-browser-based resources such as APIs, login shells, or workload management systems.

Furthermore, the AARC BPA distinguishes between two higher level logical AAI Service types based on their role within an AAI implementation: the *Community AAI* and the *Infrastructure Proxy*. Both types of AAI services may comprise the same interfaces (e.g. a proxy), but their functionality and their organisational purposes differ.

3.1 Community AAI

The purpose of the Community AAI is to enable a Research Community to manage its members and to streamline their access to services within the scope of their community activities. These services can be internal to the community itself or can be provided to the community by third-party service providers.

User authentication to the Community AAI uses primarily institutional credentials from national identity federations in eduGAIN, but, if permitted by the community, can also use other IdPs. A critical part in the Community AAI is the Community Membership Management component. This functionality allows communities to register and manage their members in accordance with their own policies. Community membership and other roles and rights that are relevant for gaining access to services are recorded in the Community Attribute Services and exposed to services via a proxy or other forms of provisioning.

The Community AAI follows the proxy-based architecture shown in Figure 1. It can therefore add attributes to the federated identity that in turn can enable services to control access to their resources. Furthermore, the Community AAI is responsible for dealing with the complexity of using different identity providers with the services offered to the community.

3.2 Infrastructure Proxy

The Infrastructure Proxy uses similar components and technologies as the Community AAI. However, the Infrastructure Proxy performs a very different role, as it is tasked to provide access to resources made available by an Infrastructure. The Infrastructure Proxy, enables Infrastructures with a large number of resources, to provide them through a single integration point, where the Infrastructure can maintain centrally all the relevant policies and business logic for making available these resources to multiple communities.

3.3 Implementation considerations

The roles of the Community AAIs and the Infrastructure Proxies are depicted in Figure 2. This view illustrates how community-specific services only need to connect to a single identity provider, i.e. their Community AAI. In contrast, generic services connect to multiple Community AAIs in order to serve different communities.

Figure 2: Researchers access resources through services using their institutional (eduGAIN), social or community-managed IdP via their Community AAI. Community services are connected to a single Community AAI, whereas generic services can be connected to more than one Community AAI. Infrastructure

services are connected to different Community AAls through a single infrastructure SP proxy.

Being connected to multiple Community AAls requires those generic services to provide some form of IdP discovery, to be able to redirect the user to the relevant Community AAI. Additionally, to allow “community branding” of the service and automatically redirecting the user to the corresponding Community AAI, the generic services may support some means of doing “IdP hinting” (see [\[AARC-G049\]](#) and [\[AARC-G061\]](#)).

Communities may also require access to various services which themselves are behind (another) proxy. This could for example be resources offered by e-Infrastructures or Research Infrastructures (Infrastructures hereafter). These “Infrastructure Proxies” can be connected to multiple Community AAls (see Figure 3). So, just as for the generic services, Infrastructure services should be able to hint to the Infrastructure Proxy which Community AAI to use (see [\[AARC-G049\]](#) and [\[AARC-G061\]](#)).

The Community AAI can therefore provide a centralised point for managing authorisation policies within the community. By doing so, authorisation policies can be shared across federated services and resources, simplifying the management process and ensuring consistency in applying authorisation.

It should be noted that this approach does not impose a requirement on communities to deploy and operate a Community AAI on their own. Communities could make use of either dedicated or multi-tenant AAI services. A multi-tenant AAI service is usually provided by a third-party infrastructure operator and can support multiple communities (tenants), as depicted in Figure 3. It typically appears as a single entity to its connected IdPs and SPs. Such multi-tenant deployments are aimed at medium-to-small research communities/groups or individual researchers. Yet it should be emphasised that also in the multi-tenant AAI scenario, the community managers are responsible for managing their community members, groups and authorisation attributes.

Figure 3: Multi-tenant deployment of AAI services following the AARC BPA architecture.

4 EOSC AAI

The process of establishing trust relationships between the AAI services within EOSC is streamlined through the EOSC AAI Federation. This enables AAI services to trust each other without the need for bilateral agreements, which simplifies the process of sharing services and resources within EOSC.

Figure 4. EOSC AAI Federation

As shown in Figure 4, members of the EOSC AAI Federation include:

- organisations providing Services to the EOSC;
- organisations operating Proxies that aggregate other service providers or enrich identities;
- and providers of authentication Identities whose identities are used by EOSC services or by EOSC proxies

Members can register the entities above in the EOSC AAI Federation Registry and have their metadata published in the EOSC AAI Federation metadata. Members may also be members of a peer federation of the EOSC AAI Federation. In such a case, they are not required to register any entities that are already registered in a peer federation (e.g. eduGAIN).

Although the EOSC AAI Federation policies and practices are technologically agnostic, support for multilateral federation is still under development in OpenID Connect. The initial implementation of the EOSC AAI Federation relies on SAML2 for the federation aspects. This means that services or authentication providers, which will be using OpenID Connect will have to use an OpenID Connect to SAML2 proxy layer in order to participate in the EOSC AAI Federation. The technical requirements for the participating entities are defined in Annex A.

The initial implementation of the EOSC AAI Federation is already ongoing in the EOSC Future project.

The EOSC AAI Task Force should re-evaluate the status of the multilateral federations in OpenID Connect and provide guidance for the future evolution of the EOSC AAI Federation.

4.1 Consistent user experience and interfaces for service providers

Accessing resources in an environment with multiple authentication options such as EOSC, requires users to select their Identity Provider (IdP). The selection of the IdP is typically assisted by IdP Discovery Services (also termed “WAYF” - Where Are You From) that enable users to find and select their IdP. In the EOSC AAI architecture, the service that the user tries to access is usually not directly connected to the authenticating IdP (i.e. the IdP identifying the user as in [\[SAML2Core Sec. 3.4.1.5\]](#)). Instead, the connection is through one or more upstream SP-IdP-proxies. The service and each of these SP-IdP-proxies need to be able to route the user authentication request to the IdP interface of the next upstream SP-IdP-Proxy until the authentication request reaches the authenticating IdP. Each time an SP-IdP-Proxy is connected to more than one upstream SP-IdP-proxies or IdPs, the SP-IdP-Proxy will have to rely on an IdP discovery mechanism where the user will need to provide input about the preferred upstream path. For example, users may need to first select their Community AAI and then select the IdP of their Home Organisation, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Identity Provider discovery in EOSC

This multi-step IdP selection process can be frustrating in some cases. The problem is further aggravated if the discovery includes both authenticating IdPs (e.g. academic IdPs from eduGAIN, social media) and Proxies. In this case, the end-user needs to identify the correct authentication path; for instance use their authenticating IdP directly or via their Community AAI. Depending on the authentication path, the same user may access the service with a different identifier (e.g. at one point with the identifier assigned by their home organisation and at another point with the identifier assigned by their Community AAI). Furthermore, when a service controls access based on the user's groups and roles within their Community AAI then users will not be able to access that service directly through their authenticating IdP.

The user experience can be improved with the adoption of the AARC “hinting” specifications that define a generic browser-based protocol for enabling entities to produce and send hints to simplify the discovery process. Specifically:

1. The `aarc_idp_hint` hint ([AARC-G061](#)) can be used for routing the user to the correct upstream proxy or authenticating IdP; for example, an infrastructure service that allows access to specific communities can use the `aarc_idp_hint` hint to route users to the Community AAI proxies
2. The `aarc_ds_hint` hint ([AARC-G062](#)) can be used for routing the user to a specific Discovery Service for selecting their preferred Identity Provider;
3. The `aarc_service_hint` hint ([AARC-G063](#)) can be passed onto the Discovery Service to present the user with information about the service that requested authentication, and/or adapt the presentation of Identity Provider options for that service (e.g. remove specific IdPs or highlight preferred ones).

Furthermore, the Community-based Entity Category, as defined in [\[AARC-G079\]](#), can be used to tailor discovery and other aspects of the user experience. Specifically:

1. Allow to distinguish Community AAls from authenticating IdPs during discovery;
2. Enable services that control access based on community identity attributes (for example community-managed groups and roles) to filter out IdPs that don't assert this Entity Category Support attribute (see Section 2 of [\[AARC-G079\]](#)); conversely, services that don't rely on community identity attributes can include only authenticating IdPs during discovery;
3. Facilitate IdP decisions to release a defined set of attributes to services.

The EOSC AAI Task Force should evaluate further improvements to this problem, including guidelines for an EOSC Login button that could be used across service providers.

4.2 Multi-infrastructure workflows

The current architecture works very well when the user is consuming services directly. One very common set of use cases though include the ability for a service agent to be able to act autonomously, on behalf of the user, consuming services and resources. If the services consumed by the agent are behind the same proxy, the current architecture works. For those cases, though, where an agent running on Service A needs to access resources on Service B, which might be connected by a different proxy, there is no straight-forward solution at the moment. So, currently, services need to trust the same proxy to support those use cases. A solution for dynamically establishing trust in a distributed environment is provided by the OpenID Connect Federation [[OIDCFed](#)]. The OAuth 2.0 Token Proxied Introspection [[AARC-G052](#)] is meant to be a temporary measure until OpenID Connect Federation is widely available. This interim solution is based on an extension of the OAuth 2.0 Token Introspection specification [[RFC7662](#)] that allows OAuth 2.0 Authorization Servers to determine the set of metadata for a given token presented to them by an OAuth 2.0 client by proxying the introspection request to the Authorisation Server that issued that token.

The EOSC AAI Task Force should re-evaluate potential solutions to this problem. Specifically it will work with the AARC Community in order to define a mechanism for the scalable establishment of trust between OAuth2 Authorization Servers. This topic is related to the support of multilateral federations in OpenID Connect.

4.3 Growth of EOSC beyond the research and education community

The current architecture enables access through more than 5100 academic identity providers registered in eduGAIN. Users without an account on an academic Identity Provider are still able to use social media or other authentication providers (e.g. ORCID) for accessing services.

To further expand access outside the research and education user base, users should be allowed to use their eIDAS enabled digital identities. This will be supported with the eIDAS proxy service that has been implemented by GEANT and the Swedish Research Council in the context of the Connecting Europe Facility, thereby opening services to all user groups including researchers and members of business organisations.

Furthermore, organisations beyond the research and education community can provide identity authentication to EOSC services as follows:

- The organisation becomes a member of a national identity federation in order to register the authenticating entity; or
- The EOSC AAI Federation Operator imports the authenticating entity of that organisation into the federation. Organisations of which such entities are discretionarily imported SHALL NOT become Members of the EOSC AAI Federation.

In both cases above, the entities MUST meet the technical requirements defined in Annex A. With respect to identity assurance, the EOSC AAI Task Force will also evaluate the minimum requirements for assurance levels.

4.4 User and community attributes and authorisation

There is a general need for different - not only community-controlled - attribute/access management services. As already described in Chapter 3, the authorisation process for accessing services may be based on a combination of information coming from more than one source, including an Infrastructure proxy operating its own attribute management service. In these cases, attributes can be specific to other contexts, not necessarily managed by a community.

It should be noted that the EOSC AAI leverages two entity categories for the consistent release of user and community attributes, respectively:

1. Personalised Entity Category [[REFEDS-Person](#)]
2. Community-based Access Entity Category [[AARC-G079](#)]

The mechanism by which the entity categories above provide for consistent attribute release is through the definition of a set of commonly supported and consumed attributes required for effective user- and community-based access to services.

5 Security considerations

The traditional "one-size-fits-all" centralised approach to authentication and authorization often falls short in decentralised environments such as the EOSC ecosystem of infrastructure components and communities of researchers. Different systems, research applications, communities and users may have varying levels of needs to secure their sensitive data and algorithms, making it impractical to enforce uniform security measures across the board.

By adopting a risk-based approach, infrastructure providers and collaborations can prioritise their focus on areas of higher risk. This approach involves assessing factors such as the sensitivity of the data or resources being accessed, the identities of the users or communities making the request, the security posture of the research infrastructures involved, and any other contextual information available. By analysing these factors, organisations can tailor the security measures accordingly and ensure that resources are appropriately protected while minimising unnecessary friction for users.

As discussed in Chapter 3, the proposed EOSC AAI Architecture enables a wide range of control points, including the research community, the infrastructure proxy and the end-service level. Ultimately this gives organisations within EOSC the flexibility to adapt to the varying risk profiles and requirements of different use cases and choose and use the control points best suited to their security requirements.

For the secure operation of attribute authorities, attribute aggregators, and proxies within the EOSC AAI, it is essential to adhere to the minimum requirements and best practices outlined in

[[AARC-G071](#)]. This document provides comprehensive guidance on operational security processes as well as requirements on traceability, auditability, and logging.

6 Work Ahead

This chapter describes the main challenges that need to be addressed in the next iterations of the EOSC AAI Architecture:

- The initial implementation of the EOSC AAI Federation relies on SAML2 for the federation aspects. The EOSC AAI Task Force will work with the AARC Community for defining a mechanism to support the scalable establishment of trust between the OAuth2 Authorization Servers that participate in the EOSC AAI Federation. The status of the multilateral federations in OpenID Connect will be re-evaluated and guidance will be provided for the future evolution of the EOSC AAI Federation.
- The EOSC AAI Task Force will provide guidance for further improving the identity provider discovery process. To this end, it will evaluate the introduction of an EOSC Login button that can be used across service providers to provide a consistent user experience.
- Addressing the critical aspect of data protection is paramount. The EOSC AAI Task Force will integrate best current practices in federated authentication and authorisation, including the REFEDS Data Protection Code of Conduct v2 [[DPCoCo](#)]. This guidance will aid EOSC AAI participants in understanding and complying with the requirements set by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

It's important to note that the EOSC AAI Task Force is currently in the process of preparing a report outlining the requirements for the EOSC AAI. This report will also serve as a guiding force for the next iteration of the EOSC AAI Architecture, namely v2023.

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Annex A: Technical Requirements

A.1 SAML entity technical requirements

Identity Providers and Service Providers supporting the SAML protocol MUST comply with the SAML2int SAML 2.0 Interoperability Deployment Profile [[SAML2int](#)].

A.1.1 Metadata

Identity Providers and Service Providers supporting the SAML protocol MUST provide a SAML 2.0 Metadata document representing its entity according to the SAML2int SAML 2.0 Interoperability Deployment Profile [[SAML2int](#)] and the recommendations for upstream metadata produced by eduGAIN participants [[eduGAIN-BCP](#)].

A.1.2 Entity Identifier Format

For entities supporting the SAML protocol, the entity identifier is the SAML entityID attribute. Values of the entityID attribute registered MUST be an absolute URI using the http, https or urn schemes.

https-scheme URIs are RECOMMENDED for all entities.

http-scheme and https-scheme URIs used for entityID values MUST contain a host part whose value is a DNS domain.

A.1.3 Scope Format

For Identity Provider entities supporting the SAML protocol, scopes MUST be rooted in the DNS domain namespace, expressed in lowercase. Multiple scopes are allowed.

Regular expressions representing multiple scopes MAY be used, but all DNS domains covered by the expression SHALL be included in checks by the Federation Operator for the member's right to use those domains. For these checks to be achievable by the Federation

Operator, the set of DNS domains covered by the regular expression MUST end with a domain under a public suffix – that is, a literal '.', followed by at least two DNS labels separated by literal '.' (representing a domain to be validated as "owned" by the entity owner), and ending with a '\$' anchor (e.g. (foo | bar)\.example\.com\$).

A.2 OpenID Connect / OAuth entity technical requirements

The requirements defined in this section apply to entities implementing the OpenID Connect protocol. To support user access through SAML-based Identity Providers, it is assumed that OpenID Connect relying parties are connected to AARC-compliant IdP-SP-Proxy services registered in the EOSC AAI Federation that are able to translate between SAML and OpenID Connect.

A.2.1 Metadata

Identity Providers supporting OpenID Connect MUST describe their configuration through a well-known location as a JSON document following the [\[OIDC-Discovery\]](#) specification.

Relying parties supporting OpenID Connect SHOULD retrieve the Identity Provider's configuration based on the Issuer information using the [\[OIDC-Discovery\]](#) specification.

A.2.2 Grant types

OpenID Connect relying parties utilising the authorization grant type SHOULD use PKCE [\[RFC7636\]](#) in conjunction with the authorisation server in order to detect and prevent attempts to inject (replay) authorisation codes into the authorisation response. The PKCE challenges must be transaction-specific and securely bound to the user agent in which the transaction was started. OpenID Connect relying parties MAY use the "nonce" parameter of the OpenID Connect authentication request as specified in [\[OIDC-Core\]](#) in conjunction with the corresponding ID Token claim for the same purpose. It is NOT RECOMMENDED to use

the implicit grant and any other response type causing the authorization server to issue an access token in the authorization response.

A.2.3 Claims

OpenID Connect relying parties MUST support requesting Claims about the End-User and the Authentication event using specific scope values as described in [\[OIDC-Core\]](#). Requesting individual Claims using the claims request parameter as defined in [\[OIDC-Core\]](#) SHOULD also be supported.

Claims which are not part of the standard set of claims defined in [\[OIDC-Core\]](#) SHOULD be requested following the mapping recommendations described in [\[OIDC-REFEDS\]](#).

A.2.4 Redirection URIs

OpenID Connect relying parties MUST pre-register one or more Redirection URI to which authentication responses from the OpenID Connect Identity Provider will be sent. The Identity Provider MUST utilise exact matching of the redirect URI specified in an authentication request against the pre-registered URIs [\[OAuth2-BCP\]](#), with the matching performed as described in [\[RFC3986\]](#) (Simple String Comparison). Redirection URIs MUST use the schemata defined in Section 3.1.2.1 of the [\[OIDC-Core\]](#) specification.

